

Semantic Data Modeling for the Census Database Deliverable 3 - Easydb Model Implementation

As a part of WP3 (Easydb Data Modeling) of the proposal, Takin.solutions, in correlation with Programmfabrik and the HU Census team, has designed and proposed additional easydb fields based on the model structure designed within WP2. The new fields are meant to be implemented into the easydb upgraded version 'fy1r' and to serve the purpose of helping accommodate the conceptual data structure in its entirety and complexity. The various field and data recipes have been regularly discussed with and eventually submitted to Programmfabrik for implementation. The completion of this stage was essential for the full development, the implementation, and the testing of the ETL pipeline in the following WP4 (ETL Pipeline Development).

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